

Effect of Paclobutrazol on the Reproductive System of *Semperula maculata*

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Abstract:

Among all the biological processes in the living organisms, reproduction is an important life process for survival and continuation of every race and species on the earth. Present study was designed to investigate the effect of Paclobutrazol on the reproductive system of terrestrial slug *Semperula maculata*. The animals were exposed for pre-determined median lethal concentration (3362.15 ppm) of Paclobutrazol upto 96 hours. Histological and biochemical estimation especially protein content from selected reproductive organs were carried out against effective dose of PBZ. Obtained results were interpreted for reproduction and potency.

Keywords: *LC₅₀, Paclobutrazol, Semperula maculata, Gonadal alterations, potency.*

Introduction

Environmental pollution found intensified by increase in agricultural development, industrialization and urbanization which leads to contamination of terrestrial and aquatic media (Akhtar et al., 2021). In the agriculture sectors, different chemicals were used as insecticides, pesticides, fertilizers and phyto regulators to increase the yield of plants. Extensive usage of such chemicals in the agricultural field has negative consequences on ecosystem (Sun et al., 2012). Now a days prominent adverse effects on non targeted species were observed with use of agricultural chemicals which increases problems with environmental and animal sensitivity (Rosell et al., 2008).

Among agriculture chemicals, phyto regulators or plant growth regulators are act as promoters or inhibitors to maintain plant health and productivity (Lewandowska et al., 2012).

Chemically paclobutrazol (PBZ) is the synthetic triazole which acts as inhibitor of gibberellin and can promote plant growth and development (Castro et al., 2004). Baris et al., (2010), provided information regarding the highest concentration of PBZ detected in groundwater was 4.2 µg/L. However, experimental data showed that, in soil PBZ can accumulate to levels as high as 150 mg/kg per dry soil at soil injection sites (MDAR, 2012).

Among invertebrates, molluscs are soft bodied, unsegmented animals with a body organized into muscular foot, head and visceral mass which containing most of the organ system. The phylum mollusc is the second largest phylum after arthropods. It has about 1, 00,000 species yet to described (Pyron and Brown, 2015). Molluscs were found sensitive model to study the aquatic and terrestrial pollution and used as pollution indicators for different compounds

(Tallarico, 2015). For providing the qualitative data about reproduction such as developmental conditions and gametogenesis histology has been extensively used (Uddin, 2012). Present investigation was carried out to observe the toxic effects of paclobutrazol on different reproductive organs and its potency for gametogenesis in terrestrial slug *Semperula maculata*.

Materials and Methods

Collection and Maintenance of Animals

Among invertebrates, terrestrial slug *Semperula maculata* is shell less gastropods. Adult, herbivorous, hermaphrodite slug were collected from the Betal leaf farm (Panmala) and Banana farm at Bedug, Miraj, district Sangli, Maharashtra, India (North Latitude 16.4 to 17.1 East Latitude 73.43 to 75.00). Collection of *Semperula maculata* was done in early morning during winter season. Animals for the experiments were used as per the approval of Maharashtra State Biodiversity Board, Nagpur (MSBB/ Desk-5/ Research/623/2023-24).

Collected slugs, were carried in a aerated plastic bottle to the laboratory. Animals were kept in aerated plastic trough with lid to provide proper ventilation. Experimental animals were allowed to feed on fresh leaves of mulberry plant *Morus indica* and cabbage-*Brassica oleracea*. All the animals were kept under controlled laboratory conditions for a week of acclimatization (Trefzer et al., 2021). Animals were daily monitored and naturally dead animals were removed from trough immediately.

Toxicant and Dose Preparation

Paclobutrazol (PBZ) is plant growth regulator which govern number of the factors of development and growth within plants. White crystalline powder of (Paclobutrazol, 95%) was purchased from Himedia and stored in safe.

All acclimatized, same sized, healthy adult slugs were selected for the experiment. As per experimental design, animals were divided into two groups one as control and another experimental group i. e. LC₅₀ PBZ. For the

toxicity study slugs were exposed to predetermined LC₅₀ for Paclobutrazol at 96 hrs. i. e. 3362.15 ppm (Tendulkar and Kamble, 2023). Working dose was prepared in distilled water and DMSO was used as solvent. Every time doses were freshly prepared and intoxicated between 9.00 to 10.00 am.

For present study, 40 slugs were used, 10 slugs as control and 30 for treatment. Experiment was carried out in plastic box containing 1 Kg oven dried soil. About 250 ml of pre determined PBZ dose was sprinkled over soil and animals were exposed upto the 96 hrs. The dose was daily spread on soil. After completion of exposure period control and experimental animal were dissected for desired reproductive organs. Interested organs such as ovatestis, penis, dart glands and prostate gland were subjected for histological and biochemical analysis.

Histology by Harris Haematoxylin and Eosin

All Reproductive organs were fixed in Bouin's solution (75 ml Picric acid + 25 ml Formalin + 5 ml Acetic acid) up to 24 hrs. at room temperature. Tissues were dehydrated followed by clear in xylene and embedded in paraffin wax. Sectioned at 4- 5 μ by using rotary microtome and stained with Haematoxylin - Eosin staining technique (Harries, 1900). Paraffin section were deparaffinised, hydrated and then stained in haematoxylin for 15 minute, washed rapidly in water then, counter stained with 1% eosin solution for 2 minutes. Stained sections were dehydrated in alcohol and cleared in xylene, DPX mounted sections were observed under microscope for histopathological assessment.

Estimation of Protein by Lowry's Method

Protein was estimated by using (Lowry, 1951). Tissue was homogenated in chilled saline solutions by using chilled mortar and pestle. Homogenate was centrifuged at 3000 rpm, the supernatant used for estimation of protein estimation by using Lowry's reagents and folin phenol reagent. The sample was incubated at room temperature for 30 min. OD was measured at 660 nm.

Statistical Analysis

The data were expressed as mean \pm with Standard deviation for each group. The threshold of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$ and $p > 0.05$ indicates as *, **, *** and non-significant respectively.

Results

For present work, reproductive organs as shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 of terrestrial slug *Semperula maculata*, Ovatestis, Dart gland, Penis and Prostate gland were selected for histological study. The morphological and biochemical changes observed under microscope were as follows.

Figure 1. Terrestrial Slug - *Semperula maculata*

Figure 2. Reproductive System of *Semperula maculata*

Ovatestis

Anatomical structure of ovatesties showed that both male and female reproductive cells develop in same organ intermingled together. Structurally ovatestis is round, globular, bulgy cell mass having approximately 0.4 ± 0.1 cm in diameter and weighing about 50 ± 3 mg as shown in Fig. 3 (A). Wangsomnuk et al., (1997) observed that in *Indoplanorbis exustus*, anatomically ovotestis as the major organ of reproduction sin association of other visceral organs.

Ovatestis is major reproductive organ *S. maculata* is considered as hermaphrodite slug similar to other stylommatophora species *Arion ater* (Parivar, 1978), *Deroceras reticulatum* (Bailey, 1973 and Runham, 1978) and *Megalobulimus abbreviates* (Horn, 2005). Ovatestis consist of a number of follicles. The growing oocytes were observed with prominent nuclei and nucleoli. The control sectional view of ovatestis in Fig 3 (B) showed scattered spermatocytes and mature spermatids. Spermatocyte I in the meiotic prophase and spermatocytes II in the rosette-forming form were observed in the control section of ovatestis

After the 96 hrs. exposure, (Fig. 3(C)) it was observed that spermatocytes were more disturbed and internal content is hypertropic. Follicular structure was disrupted. Growing pre-

vitellogenic oocytes and early vitellogenic oocyte were vacuolated and some without nucleoli. After acute exposure for long time, intensity of sperm was decreased.

Figure 3. A) Whole Mount of Ovatestis of *Semperula maculata*;
B) T.S. of Ovatestis of *Semperula maculata* for Control at 400X Magnification;
C) T. S. of Ovatestis of *Semperula maculata* Exposed to LC₅₀ of PBZ after 96hrs. at 400 X Magnification. (Ct- Connective tissue, Sc- Secretory cells Lc- Luminal content, acini);
D) Dart Gland of *Semperula maculata*;
E) T.S. of Dart Gland of *Semperula maculata* for Control at 400 X Magnification;
F) T. S. of Dart Gland of *Semperula maculata* Exposed to LC 50 of PBZ after 96 hrs. at 400 X Magnification. (Pgc – Peripheral glandular cells, Lc- Luminal content)

Dart Gland

Anatomically as showed in Fig. 3 (D) dart gland is long cylindrical, fibrous in nature with area of 2.1 ± 0.15 cm length and 0.3 ± 0.12 cm width. Normal histology of dart gland (Fig. 1 (E)) showed large glandular cells which found peripherally arranged with basal uninucleated circular cells, muscular layer with luminal space in it. When stained with Hematoxylin-Eosin, luminal region showed several granular secretory cells and droplets.

Dart gland of terrestrial slug *Semperula maculata* showed alterations in the internal architecture as shown in (Fig.3- F). After 96 hrs. of PBZ exposure, prominently enlarged, hypertrophic cells were found in peripheral arranged glandular part. Internal luminal content was scattered. Glandular cells were found damaged and ruptured. Overall dart gland was morphologically lost its normal cellular cytometry.

Penis

As shown in Fig. 4 (A) Anatomically penis is long, cylindrical organ with length of 0.64 ± 0.15 cm of length and 0.24 ± 0.11 cm of width. In experimental animal penis is covered with thin chitinous sheath. Thin protective connectives tissue was found on the outer part of penis, internally followed by muscular layer. Histologically penis sheath was embedded with a small group of multicellular glands and internal

unicellular glands was observed (Fig. 4 (B)). Under magnification these glands were more numerous and prominently located internally for secretion.

After 96 hrs. of PBZ exposure, (Fig 4 (C)) glandular portion of the penis became hypertrophic and intracellular content was found disturbed. Internal lumen shows dilation in muscle fibers.

Figure 4. A) Whole Mount of Penis of *Semperula maculata*;

B) T.S. of Penis of *Semperula maculata* for Control at 400X Magnification;

C) T. S. of Penis of *Semperula maculata* Exposed to LC_{50} of PBZ after 96hrs. at 400 X Magnification. (Ps- Penis sheath, L- Lumen UG – Unicellular glands MG – Multicellular glands, Pm – penis muscles);

D) Prostate Gland of *Semperula maculata*;

E) T.S. of Prostate Gland of *Semperula maculata* for Control at 400 X Magnification;

F) T. S. of Prostate Gland of *Semperula maculata* Exposed to LC_{50} of PBZ after 96 hrs. at 400 X Magnification. (Sc- Secretory cells, Lc- Luminal content Ct -Connective tissue)

Prostate Gland

Anatomy prostate gland as showed in Fig. 4 (D) is leaf like white coloured cell mass with $1.32 \pm$

0.13 cm of length and 0.68 ± 0.1 cm of width. In Fig. 4 (E) showed the normal histology of Prostate gland with numerous secretory cells

arranged in lobules, which was covered by thin connective tissues whereas luminal linings were lined by secretory epithelial cells. Secretory cells were normally arranged indicating its normal biomechanics in support to reproduction. After the exposure of PBZ for 96 hrs. prostate gland of *S. maculata* showed some morphological and histological alterations as shown in (Fig. 4 (F)) histologically cells were prominently dilated, some were damaged and connective tissues were found scattered in sectional view. Secretory cells were lost its normal size and shape some of which were enlarged and hypertropic, due to loss of some cells, internal gap was seen in the section.

Biochemical Study – Protein Estimation

Biochemical component of every animals are associated with its rate of metabolism and

availability of micromolecules essential to maintain metabolic rate. In the selected animal major component in the reproductive organs were carbohydrate, protein and lipid content. In the development these components play vital role to undergo gonadal functional maturity.

Proteins are the macromolecules and important building blocks for metabolism and play vital role in different biological processes. Under the conditions of PBZ toxicity protein level from the selected organs found decreased. Effect of paclobutrazol and estimated values of protein content from reproductive organ in control and experimental group of the Slug *S. maculata* as shown in Table No. 1 comparative data was shown in Graph No. 1.

Table 1. Effect of Paclobutrazol on the Protein Content ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ Wet Weight of Tissue) of Reproductive Organs of the Slug *S. maculata*

Reproductive Organs	Control	PBZ LC ₅₀ after exposure of 96 hours	p Value
Ovatestis	22.066±2.045	17.85±2.150	***
Dart Gland	39.483±2.254	22.6±1.391	***
Penis	42.366±1.181	23.7±1.639	***
Prostate Gland	45.932±1.773	25.766±1.233	***

Graph 1. PBZ Induced Changes in the Protein Content of Reproductive Organs of *S. maculata*

Note: Values of \pm indicates standard deviation. p value - $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$ and $p > 0.05$ indicates as *, **, *** and non-significant respectively.

Ovatestis

The control group of slug *S. maculata* showed $22.066 \pm 2.045 \mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ protein concentration in the ovatestis which was decreased in LC₅₀ group of paclobutrazol i.e. $17.85 \pm 2.150 \mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$.

Dart Gland

Dart gland from the control group of *S. maculata* showed protein concentration $39.483 \pm 2.254 \mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$. In experimental group protein content was decreases $22.6 \pm 1.391 \mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ as compared to control group.

Penis

In control group of slug *S. maculata* showed $42.366 \pm 1.181 \mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ of protein concentration in the penis. After the exposure of predetermined LC₅₀ of paclobutrazol to the penis, it showed maximum decrease in the protein concentration i.e., $23.7 \pm 1.639 \mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$.

Prostate Gland

Protein concentration was 45.932 ± 1.773 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ in prostate gland of control group. but in experimental group showed depletion in the protein content $25.766 \pm 1.233\mu\text{g}/100$ mg as compare to control group.

Discussion

In the developing country like India in which agricultural revolution has made tremendous change in the farming sector. Paclobutrazol has been permitted for use on food crops in Australia, New Zealand, South Africa, India, Philippines, Vietnam, Canada, USA (California), Finland, Hungary, Greece, Cyprus, Denmark and Netherlands (Davis and Curry, 1991). In India, PBZ was registered and commercially available as a plant growth regulator under Section 9 (3) of the Insecticides Act 1968 by the Central Board of Insecticides and Registration in November, 2009 (Kegley et al., 2010). Wang, (2019) stated that, in agriculture and floriculture PBZ has been widely used by directly applying to the soil.

The concentration of PBZ used by farmers ranges from tens to thousands of ppm. Long-term use, high stability, and mobility of PBZ have caused the researchers to begin considering the potential ecological risk posed by residual and accumulated PBZ in soil and water. Yekti et al., (2014), demonstrate that the PBZ is highly toxic to *Danio rerio* mainly affects the developmental stages during embryonic development and decreases the survival rate and hating rate. (Thakur and Kaur, 2017) reported, gastropods like snails and slugs were widely distributed in different geographical regions, and provide as excellent representatives of environmental pollution, therefor used as most sensitive biological tool. (Londhe et al., 2020) documented, behavioural and histological alterations in the reproductive system of *S. maculata* after induction of cobalt nitrate, in our study we also have observed the similar kind of alterations. (Ghane et al., 2017) observed, higher concentration of PBZ cased stress in *Oreochromis mossambicus* which has resulted to depletion in the

carbohydrate, protein and fat content from body may be to intoxication. In general intoxication impact was analysed by elevated ammonia-N excretion through excretion.

Nakadera, (2013) documented that, Prostate gland secreted seminal fluid which found essential for fertilization, and also helped by various ways to gain paternity. Londhe et al., (2015), studied the effect of mercury chloride against reproductive organs of *Semperula maculata* and documented that intoxication of mercury declines the reproductive capacity by cellular damage and biochemical reduction over gametogenesis it was severely affected and declined. Lettieri et al., (2018), studies toxic effect of copper on the reproductive system on the gonads, spermatozoa and protamine-like [PL] proteins of *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. Kumar et al., (2011) reported the effect of *Syzygium aromaticum* on the ovatestis of *Lymnaea acuminata* after treated with LC_{50} for 96 hrs. depletes the biochemical content free amino acids, proteins and nucleic acids.

Conclusion

In present investigation dose of paclobutrazol was found moderately toxic to the terrestrial slug *Semperula maculata*. Predetermined PBZ dose (LC_{50} - 33362.15 ppm) caused histopathological changes in reproductive organs including ovatestis, penis, dart gland and prostate glands. Dose of PBZ has induced prominent cellular damage as hyperretropic and cellular rupturing in gonadal cells. Some gametic cells were lost the capacity for proliferation and leading to declined rate of gametogenesis.

Biochemically protein content of gonadal cells were found declined and may be due to metabolism limited to support the capacity of gametogenesis. The energetics of reproductive tract has several impact on reproductive ability and behavioural pattern of selected molluscsn terrestrial slug. Likewise, number and potential of selected animal may get disturbed with natural homeostasis. Therefore, reducing toxicant we can save the animals and conserve them in the natural habitat. Further study in this regard is

going on in the Animal physiology and Toxicology laboratory.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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